

The Rhetoric of Hybrid Publishing

Negotiating
Legitimacy and
Stigma in the
Modern Publishing
Landscape

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Prepared for the
**Summer Undergraduate
Research Grant**

Abstract

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Hybrid publishing has emerged as a disruptive force in today's literary landscape, challenging traditional notions of legitimacy, authorship, and artistic authority.

Defined by the Independent Book Publishers Association (IBPA) through [11 points of criteria](#) as an author-subsidized model, hybrid publishing combines professional standards of traditional publishing with financial investment by authors. Unlike self-publishing services companies, reputable hybrid publishers vet submissions, maintain editorial integrity, abide by production standards, deliver comprehensive distribution beyond Amazon, and offer authors a higher-than-standard share of sales revenue.

This study presents a rhetorical analysis of how hybrid publishing is framed in public and institutional discourse. Using digital ethnography, literature review, and qualitative interviews with authors, editors, and publishing professionals, it examines how legitimacy is constructed, contested, and redefined. Findings reveal the rhetorical strategies authors and publishers use to navigate credibility, the ethical implications of publishing models, and the cultural power dynamics shaping the industry. This research contributes to understanding access, equity, and creative agency in a rapidly evolving publishing ecosystem.

Introduction

600 Years in the Making

A decorative graphic consisting of a series of blue diagonal lines that create a sense of depth and movement, positioned to the left of the text.

Even after 600+ years, publishing remains a dynamic and evolving industry, driven by technological, conceptual, and artistic innovation. The book as an object and an art form continues to hold cultural and intellectual value, inspiring widespread interest in both its creation and dissemination. Traditional publishers have long positioned themselves as gatekeepers of culture, truth, and wisdom, conferring legitimacy upon the authors they select. Renowned Italian publisher Roberto Calasso further underscores the tenacious nature of the book writing, “the book has already encountered difficult times and has always endured . . . at worst, there’s an attempt to treat it like an endangered species, to be corralled in a large national park” (46). This notion that the book is a rare and culturally cherished object reinforces the mystique of traditional publishing and the desire of authors to have their work validated by a prestigious press.

Hybrid publishing, however, turns this dynamic on its head. Rather than relying on external validation from a traditional publisher, authors must become the origin of their own perceived value. The model shifts the capital risk from publisher to author, requiring them to invest in the production, distribution, and marketing of their work while retaining higher creative and financial control. Michael Castleman author of *The Untold Story of Books: A Writers History of Publishing*, paints the history of the publishing industry in three eras, and the first era—the longest era—ran until the late 19th century, and was a time when publishers had yet to exist. “In a world without publishers, most authors were entrepreneurs who hired printers, paid to publish, and marketed their books on their own” (20). In this sense, hybrid publishing marks a return to the original era of publishing which leaned on the legitimacy of the author, not the publisher, to tell their story. Hybrid publishing offers an alternative pathway where the author can be both creator and investor again.

Description

A Unique Position

Author and industry journalist Jane Friedman differentiates hybrid publishing from vanity presses in the second edition of her book, *The Business of Being a Writer*. “Is this company charging significant fees for simply distributing the book (e.g., making your book available for sale through Amazon),” she writes, “or is this company charging fees based on how many print books you buy? If either is true, you’re firmly in the realm of old-school ‘vanity’ publishers that are generally considered less author-friendly than the new generation of service companies” (212).

Hybrid publishing occupies a unique position between traditional and self-publishing, by providing authors with both infrastructure and guidance while requiring financial participation from the author. Because authors in hybrid contracts are required to front capital to produce, promote, and distribute their own books, many questions arise around projected return on investment (ROI). And rightly so, as the risk has been passed from publisher to author. That’s why understanding how this model is perceived, both positively and negatively, requires examining not only the rhetoric used by authors, publishers, and industry institutions, but the dominant power structures and gatekeeping practices that have long been associated with the industry.

Methods

A Closer Look

To examine how hybrid publishing operates rhetorically within the broader publishing ecosystem, I employed a multi-method, humanities-based approach including a literature review, digital ethnography, and qualitative interviews.

First, I conducted an extensive review of contemporary literature in publishing studies. Much of the most relevant material came from historical accounts of the industry, which provided essential context for understanding how economic models, legitimacy, and authority have evolved over time. The changes we see today in the publishing industry are happening at both a technological and monetary level. Amazon in particular has kicked the door wide open with Kindle Direct Publishing (KDP) and Print-on-Demand (POD) services. This has given many debut authors a low to no cost pathway for putting their work out into the world. But sometimes good things come strapped with consequences, and Amazon's KDP has led to a flooded market of full of self-published titles—titles that don't always bear the mark of rigorous editorial and design production.

Next, I conducted **semi-structured interviews** with authors, editors, hybrid and traditional publishers, and other industry professionals. These interviews offered insight into how individuals frame their experiences, justify their choices, and navigate the perception of what content does and does not have value. I built a contact list of nearly 200 publishing professionals using multiple strategies: I leveraged my professional network that I have spent the last decade fostering; I reached out directly to industry leaders; and I issued open calls via personal social media channels and the [XOXO Publishing](#) Instagram account, which brands itself as, "Gossip Girl, but publishing" and reaches over 31.2k followers.

Methods (cont.)

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All interview transcripts were audit-edited for clarity following the Oral History Association Principles and Best Practices, as well as Columbia University's [Oral History Transcription Style Guide](#). Reflexive phrases (e.g., "well," "so," "kind of") were removed unless meaningful, while non-lexical sounds (e.g., "uh," "um") were omitted. False starts and unfinished sentences were preserved and marked with an em dash (—). Brackets indicate supplied or missing words. Participants were invited to member-check transcripts to ensure accuracy. All interviews were conducted within the scope of the IRB's recommendations and approval.

The digital ethnography involved reviewing 39 Reddit posts from the past four years, including one post titled, "[What's the Difference Between Self-Publishing and Hybrid Publishers?](#)" as far back as 15 years ago. These posts were especially telling of author perceptions of the hybrid model relative to self-publishing and vanity publishing. Author opinions on Reddit were often shaped by Yog's Law, a term coined by John MacDonald in the early aughts, to describe the concept that the "money should always flow to the author." Meaning an author should never pay to publish.

Lastly, I analyzed the branding and rhetoric of nearly 35 active hybrid publishing companies. I compared and contrasted information on their websites that addressed contracts, rights ownership, production timelines, and keywords. The most prevalent keyword phrases I found were "shared risk model," "partner publishing," "author-subsidized," "best of both worlds," "pathways to publishing," "author centric," and "relationship publishing," which I think reflects the strategy and approach of many publishers aiming to distinguish from vanity presses.

Interview Participants & Categorical Breakdown

In Conversation

A total of 187 publishing professionals were contacted. Of these, 27 declined, 113 did not respond, seven initially agreed but could not participate, and one contributed via LinkedIn chat. Thirty-nine participants were interviewed via one-hour Zoom sessions.

One notable limitation of this study is the absence of interviews with literary agents, who continue to function as important gatekeepers between authors and traditional publishers. Hybrid publishing often bypasses these intermediaries by connecting authors directly with publishers and offering alternative financial arrangements, such as retaining rights and earning higher royalty rates, sometimes up to 85%, on the back end instead of a traditional advance. Future research incorporating agent perspectives could further illuminate how hybrid publishing reshapes the power dynamics and economic relationships within the publishing ecosystem.

Participants (alphabetical)

Naren Aryal
Amplify Publishing,
CEO + Publisher

Olivia J. Bennett
Author;
Freelance Editor

Renita Bryant
Mynd Matters Publishing,
Publisher

Nick Courtright
Atmosphere Press
Founder + CEO

Kim Daly
Workman Publishing Group
Copy Chief

David Hancock
Morgan James Publishing
Founder

Josey Hill
HarperCollins Christian Publishing,
Sales Coordinator

Maggie Langrick
Wonderwell Press,
Founding Publisher

Thad McIlroy
The Future of Publishing,
Publishing Technology
Analyst and Author

Leslie Miller (LAM)
Girl Friday Productions,
CEO/Co-founder

April Jo Murphy
Keller Williams Realty, LLC,
Director of Publishing

Jill Smith
Denver Publishing Institute
University of Denver, Director

John Warren
George Washington University,
Program Director of Publishing

Trena White
Page Two,
Co-Chief Executive Officer

Holly Baker
Brigham Young University
Associate Professor,
Editing and Publishing Program

Rohit Bhargava
Ideapress Publishing /
The Non-Obvious Company, Founder

Rose Friel Conway
Foreword Literary Consulting,
Publishing Consultant

Dan Curran
Chapters,
Co-Founder

Andrea Fleck-Nisbet
Independent Book Publishers Association,
CEO

Jocelyn Hargrave
University of Derby,
Lecturer in Publishing

Sterling Hooker
Barnes & Noble, Freelance Editor;
Author of *To Chase a Prophecy*

Joseph Christian Lawrence
Choice Press
Head of Publishing

Madeline McIntosh
Authors Equity
CEO + Publisher

Joe Milazzo
Surveyor Book,
Founder; Author of *Crepuscule W/ Nellie*

John Rodzvilla
Emerson College,
Assistant Professor, Writing,
Literature and Publishing

Matthew Stadler
The GOAT PoL, Founder and Editor;
Author of *Landscape: Memory*

Brooke Warner
She Writes Press, Publisher

Jennifer Baum
Midwest Book Awards,
Chair

Michael Bourne
Poets & Writers Magazine,
Contributing Editor

Brunella Costagliola
The Military Editor Agency,
Ghostwriter and Editor

Logen Cure
Host, *Inner Moonlight*;
Author of *Welcome to Midland*

Jane Friedman
The Bottom Line Newsletter, Journalist;
Author of *he Business of Being a Writer*

Per Henningsgaard
Curtin University,
School of Media, Creative Arts and
Social Inquiry, Senior Lecturer

Carrie Jones
Interabang Books, Event Coordinator
+ Gift Buyer

John Maxwell
Simon Fraser University,
Associate Professor

Jonathan Merkh
Forefront Books,
President & CEO

Jim Milliot
Publishers Weekly,
Co-Editorial Director

Donna Seaman
Booklist, Adult Books Editor

Victoria Strauss
Writer Beware,
Co-Founder

Kent Watson
Book Dimensions,
Principal Director

Categorical Breakdown of Participants

39 PARTICIPANTS

**Because a majority of participants held multiple roles within the publishing industry, they were assigned to the category that best reflected their lead title.*

Analysis

Yog's Law and Beyond

Interview data revealed variable perceptions of hybrid publishing. Professionals in consulting, journalism, freelance editing, public relations, and awards judging demonstrated higher familiarity, recognizing both advantages and limitations. As I conducted more interviews, a few common themes began to emerge.

Hybrid publishing distinguishes itself from self-publishing and publishing service companies by not only providing access to professional infrastructure and editorial guidance, but by entering a title into the publisher's distribution networks, while demonstrating "respectable sales" (IBPA). However, almost unanimously, interviewees all agreed that distribution was a key component in the definition of a hybrid.

The digital ethnography further revealed much more skepticism in online communities than I anticipated. This is predominantly shaped by the concept of Yog's Law, and in the leading claim on Reddit that hybrid publishers are scammers, and that, as an author, you should never pay to publish your book. Many authors conflate hybrid publishers with vanity presses due to perceived upfront costs, although reputable hybrids adhere to IBPA standards.

Hybrid publishers that ethically serve author communities are up front about costs, collaborate closely with authors to produce high quality books, and communicate effectively about the author's goals.

Overall, the branding analysis I conducted of 35 active hybrid publishers not only revealed rhetoric emphasizing collaboration, shared risk, and author-centric practices, but that several companies notably sought to position themselves as a credible, alternative publishing pathway distinct from self-publishing or vanity models. However, one of the most striking findings is that hybrid publishers care deeply about their brands. Much of the work they acquire comes from referrals and other soft introductions. Hybrids are only as good as their worst book, so they are highly incentivized to do good work and make great books, but also to establish and maintain, deep, strong, long lasting relationships with their authors.

Analysis (cont.)

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This research challenged my initial assumptions that the lingering stigma around hybrid publishing was primarily reinforced by the Big Five publishers. Instead, familiarity with hybrid publishing was limited among traditional publishing professionals, while awareness of the model's existence was higher among consultants, freelance editors, journalists, and awards adjudicators. These professionals recognized that hybrid publishing provides opportunities for authors to access professional publishing infrastructure while retaining greater creative and financial control.

However, widespread misconceptions persist, particularly among online communities and early-career authors. Reddit and other author-driven forums frequently associate hybrid publishing with vanity or predatory models due to the perception that authors pay for access. While this concern is historically grounded, reflecting longstanding industry caution, it does not accurately represent reputable hybrid publishers, many of which adhere to IBPA's 11-point criteria and maintain rigorous editorial, production, and distribution standards.

The analysis of hybrid publisher branding demonstrates that companies themselves actively shape perceptions through language emphasizing collaboration, shared risk, and author-centered practices. By framing their model as a legitimate third pathway to publishing, distinct from both self-publishing and vanity presses, hybrid publishers rhetorically construct authority and credibility. Yet, the persistence of negative online discourse indicates that public understanding lags behind industry practices, creating ongoing challenges for hybrid publishers and their authors.

Conclusions

Contesting Space

Hybrid publishing still occupies a contested but increasingly more recognized space in contemporary publishing. Reports such as [Is it a Steal? An Investigation into 'hybrid' / paid-for publishing services](#) (The Society of Authors and The Writer's Union) frame paid-for publishing services as potentially exploitative, cautioning authors to avoid financial risk while the IBPA and reputable hybrid publishers counter this narrative by adhering to industry standards, providing editorial and production support, and maintaining ethical business practices. Even though there are lingering concerns around author investment versus ROI, reports like [The Business Book ROI Study](#) (2024) indicate that nonfiction hybrid book, especially business books, have been shown to turn a profit.

Among industry professionals and, sparingly, authors, hybrid publishing represents a viable alternative pathway for authors. Success in the model, as in traditional publishing, is not guaranteed as publishing is a very competitive industry where profit margins are often modest. However, findings indicate that hybrid publishing can enable authors to create high quality work that reaches its audience, particularly in genres like business books where financial returns are measurable. Interviews with publishing professionals indicated that authors and hybrid publishers see accomplishments when both parties are clear about their goals for the release of a book.

This study ultimately demonstrates that legitimacy in hybrid publishing is rhetorically constructed through multiple channels and communities in the industry whether that's industry professionals, branding strategies by hybrid publishers, or public discourse. Misunderstandings about the model do persist, largely due to conflation with vanity and predatory publishers in online forums, but by continuing to clarify these distinctions, this we can equip authors, scholars, and industry professionals with the knowledge needed to navigate publishing choices and engage critically with emerging models.

BEYOND BORDERS

Democratizing Knowledge in a Polarized World

NOVA SCHOOL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
LISBON, PORTUGAL

Future Application

My goals for this research extend beyond the scope of this initial report. I plan to develop the project into a comprehensive scholarly article for submission to [Publishing Research Quarterly](#). In addition, I intend to adapt the article into a trade piece for [Publishers Weekly](#) in order to reach a broader audience of publishing professionals. I have also been invited to present my findings at The George Washington University's 15th Annual [Ethics in Publishing Conference](#) (October 9–10, Washington, D.C.), where I will speak on the Equity and Inclusion in Publishing panel. Finally, I have submitted a proposal to present at the [Twenty-Fourth International Conference on Publishing Studies](#), hosted by Information, Medium & Society.

What was ultimately clear to me from my conversations with professionals in the industry was that hybrid publishing is accepted as a viable third pathway to publishing. However, lingering rhetoric around vanity presses and predatory publishers, often promulgated by authors in online forums such as Reddit, continues to create confusion about what hybrid publishing actually is. The aim of my research, and all subsequent iterations, is to define this publishing model with clarity in order to provide authors with the information they need to make an educated decision about how to bring their books to market.

Conclusion

Summary

Hybrid publishing still occupies a contested but increasingly more recognized space in contemporary publishing. Reports such as [Is it a Steal? An Investigation into 'hybrid' / paid-for publishing services](#) (The Society of Authors and The Writer's Union) frame paid-for publishing services as potentially exploitative, cautioning authors to avoid financial risk while the IBPA and reputable hybrid publishers counter this narrative by adhering to industry standards, providing editorial and production support, and maintaining ethical business practices. Even though there are lingering concerns around author investment versus ROI, reports like [The Business Book ROI Study](#) (2024) indicate that nonfiction hybrid book, especially business books, have been shown to turn a profit.

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This study ultimately demonstrates that legitimacy in hybrid publishing is rhetorically constructed through multiple channels and communities in the industry whether that's industry professionals, branding strategies by hybrid publishers, or public discourse. Misunderstandings about the model do persist, largely due to conflation with vanity and predatory publishers in online forums, but by continuing to clarify these distinctions, this we can equip authors, scholars, and industry professionals with the knowledge needed to navigate publishing choices and engage critically with emerging models.

Learning Outcomes

This research aims to provide readers with a nuanced understanding of the rhetorical and cultural dynamics of hybrid publishing, highlighting how legitimacy and authority are constructed and contested within the literary marketplace. It encourages analysis of the opportunities and challenges that hybrid publishing presents, particularly for marginalized voices, and prompts critical reflection on the ethical and ideological stakes embedded in contemporary publishing models. By engaging with these themes, participants gain insight into the ways authors and industry professionals navigate credibility, access, and creative agency in an evolving publishing landscape.

Analyze

How legitimacy and authority are shaped in hybrid publishing.

Evaluate

Opportunities and challenges for marginalized voices.

Critically Reflect

On ethical and ideological aspects of publishing models.

Understand

How authors navigate credibility and creative agency.

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Thank you!

Thank you for awarding me the Summer Undergraduate Research Grant. I truly appreciate the opportunity it has given me to expand my knowledge, grow my professional network, and contribute to the publishing industry. If you have any questions or would like to discuss my findings further, please don't hesitate to reach out.

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